

PHOTOGRAPHIC SENSITISERS DERIVED FROM QUINALDINE

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In an attempt to prepare a photographic sensitiser suitable for use in the manufacture of panchromatic plates, a set of new sensitisers has been prepared by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with quinaldine-methiodide, -ethiodide, -*n*-propyl iodide and -*n*-butyl iodide, in presence of piperidine as a catalyst. The dyeing, optical, photographic and other properties of these dyestuffs have been examined. The preparation and properties of quinaldine-*n*-propyl iodide and quinaldine-*n*-butyl iodide have been described for the first time. The future line of research for the synthesis of the proposed sensitiser has also been discussed.

In a previous communication (Doja and Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 377) it has been reported that the attempt to prepare a photographic sensitiser, which will sensitise uniformly, *without any gap*, from the blue to the red end of the spectrum, and will thus be useful in the manufacture of "panchromatic" plates, was only partly successful. The increase in the molecular weight of the dye did produce, as expected, a shift of the band of extra-sensitisation towards the red, but this was not large enough to make the compound commercially valuable. A further increase in the molecular weight of the dyestuff has now been effected, by using quinolinium compounds in place of pyridinium compounds, in the condensation with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde. These syntheses have given rise to a new set of sensitisers, represented by the general formula (J).

Like other members of the cyanine dye group these compounds are soluble in ionising solvents like water, alcohol and acetic acid, and insoluble in non-ionising solvents like ether, benzene, and chloroform. The solubility in water decreases with increasing molecular weight, the butyl iodide of the dye being nearly insoluble in this liquid. All aqueous solutions are ruby-red, and all alcoholic solutions are magenta in colour, except that of the butyl iodide, which gives a brownish yellow solution exhibiting a weak green fluorescence. This solution too turns magenta on dilution with water. The relative intensity of the alcoholic solutions (1 : 50,000) of the methiodide, ethiodide, and *n*-propyl iodide of the dyes, as determined by a Duboscq colorimeter, is given in Table I. It

* In this structure, the iodine (anion) is not attached definitely to either of the two nitrogen atoms. This is due to the fact that in a cyanine dye there is much evidence for supposing that the acidic radical of the dye is not associated with one nitrogen atom more than the other (Mills and Brannholtz, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1489; Hamer, *ibid.*, 1928, 127, 206; also see *J. Soc. Chem., Ind.*, 1922, 41, 804A; 1935, 84, 640). Otherwise expressed the positive charge of the dye is shared between the two nitrogens. There exists in fact a kind of resonance within the molecule, in which, the positive charge changes position. The actual constitution of the cation is that of a resonance hybrid of these two structures. It has been suggested that the intense colour and some other properties of the cyanine dyes are due to their resonating structures.

is noteworthy that the ethiodide (L) again (*cf.* Doja and Prasad, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 126; 377) forms the most intensely coloured solution in the series.

TABLE I

(K)	Depth of the solution of		(M)
	(L)	(M)	
12	10'05	10'02	16'15
	10'00		16'20
	10'00		16'20
7	6'40	6'40	9'00
	6'40		9'05
	6'40		9'05
Relative Intensity.	1'19	1'14	0'74
	1'09		0'77

TABLE II

Compound	Vol. of N/100-HCl required for complete decolourisation of 2 c.c. of	
	Alcoholic soln. (c.c.)	Aq. soln. (c.c.)
(K)	6'9	3'3
	7'1	
(L)	7'9	6'7
	7'9	
(M)	7'9	13'1
	8'0	
(N)	9'5	21'6
	9'4	

In Tables I-VI, (K), (L), (M), (N) refer respectively to the methiodide, ethiodide, *n*-propyl iodide and *n*-butyl iodide of the dye.

The observation of Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.* 1920, 54, 255) that alcoholic solutions of certain cyanine dyes are more resistant to decolourisation by mineral acids than their aqueous solutions, has been found to be only partly correct with this set of dyes. The solutions of the methiodide and the ethiodide do behave in this fashion, but in the case of the propyl and the butyl iodides, it is the other way round, the aqueous solution being more resistant to decolourisation than the alcoholic solution. It will be seen from Table II that there is a gradual increase in the amount of acid required for complete decolourisation as we ascend the series, this increase being much more pronounced in the case of the aqueous solutions than in the alcoholic.

Except the methiodide, the crystals are all pleochroic, and exhibit characteristic reflexes. Their melting points do not show any regularity. It is, however, interesting to note that the heaviest number of the series, the butyl iodide (N), has the lowest melting point. In Table III are recorded, the shapes, melting points, and optical properties of the crystals.

TABLE III

Compound.	Shape.	M.p.	Colour by reflected light.	Colour through transmitted light.	Reflex.	Pleochroism.		Remarks.
						Colour of light in one position of polariser.	Colour after rotation through 90°	
(K)	Aggregates of small opaque irregular crystals.	190*	Dark green.	Nil	Strong, bottle-green.	Nil	Nil	Under the microscope the crystals show a green halo with polarised light.
(L)	Minute felted needles	230	Light chocolate	Dull red	Medium, greenish blue	Orange	Scarlet	—
(M)	Microscopic needles.	198	Olive green	Dark brownish red (in thin crystals only)	Weak, light green	Reddish brown	Opaque	Shows a violet halo under the microscope with polarised light.
(N)	"Dogtooth" crystals	111	Brownish yellow.	Yellowish green	Weak, blue	Yellowish green	Brown	—

The methiodide (K), ethiodide (L), and -propyl iodide (M) dye silk, wool and cotton varying shades of blue-violet, the blue component of which increases with increasing molecular weight of the dye. The butyl-iodide (N) produces yellow shades only (Table IV). None of these colours is fast either to sunlight or to washing.

TABLE IV

Compound	Colour produced on			Remarks.
	Silk.	Wool.	Cotton.	
(K)	Violet.	Reddish violet	Light violet	In the case of (L), the ethiodide, wool can be dyed any colour from light salmon to deep blue-red by the addition of 1-5% acetic acid to the dye bath.
(L)	Blue-violet	Deep reddish violet	Reddish blue	
(M)	Deep blue-violet	Reddish blue	Brinjal blue	
(N)	Pinkish yellow	Lemon yellow	Bluish yellow	

The fluorescence of weak solutions (1:50,000) of these dyestuffs in 90% alcohol as determined by the previously described method (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 348) is given in Table V.

TABLE V

Wallace colour filter No.	Colour of the floureracent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam.			
	(K).	(L).	(M).	(N).
1	Brilliant red	Red	Dull red	Red
2	Flaming red	Scarlet	Crimson	Weak red
3	Light red	Deep pink	Vermilion red	Yellowish green
4	Weak flaming red	Pink	Rose-red	Flaming red
5	Red with slight yellow tinge	Orange	Reddish yellow	Yellow
6	Yellowish red	Weak orange	Orange	Sulphur-yellow
7	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Sky blue
8	Weak blue (seen with difficulty)	Light arc blue	Weak blue	Grass green
9	Deep blue	Sapphire blue	Blue-violet	Yellowish green
10	Yellowish red	Orange	Orange	Lemon yellow

The sensitisation spectra of these compounds are shown in Fig. 1, and the salient features of the spectra have been summarised in Table VI.

FIG. 1.

It will be seen that these compounds extend the normal sensitivity of the photographic plate fairly well into the red end of the spectrum, but the bands of extra sensitisation are weak and the "gap" in the blue-green is quite pronounced.

TABLE VI

Compound.	Total range of sensitisation.	Range of uniformly intense sensitisation.	Extra sensitisation	
			Minimum.	Maximum.
(K)	4200-6350 Å	4400-5250 Å	5250 Å	5750 Å
(L)	4200-6400	4350-5000	5200	5800
(M)	4250-6150	4400-5000	5200	5750
(N)	4200-6350	4350-5000	5300	5600

Comparatively speaking, the -ethiodide of the series is the best sensitiser, extending the sensitisation upto 6400. It is interesting to note in this connexion, that in the carbocyanine series of dyestuffs too, the -ethiodide is the best photographic sensitiser (Pope and Mills, *Phot. J.*, 1920, 44, 256). From the point of view, however, of the preparation, of a "single" sensitiser, suitable for use in the manufacture of panchromatic plates, these syntheses have not been quite successful. The replacement of pyridine nucleus by quinoline nucleus has reintroduced the chief defect of "red" sensitisers—the failure to sensitise photographic plates for a short region in the blue-green portion of the spectrum. Future attempts, therefore, to increase the size of the original substance, 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine methiodide (P) (Mills and Pope, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

1922, 121, 946), with a view to extend its sensitising power farther into the red (Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1930, 70, 376; Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 129, 995), should not disturb the pyridine molecule, which, in some way seems to be responsible for the valuable "uniform" sensitiveness of this compound. Another method of achieving our object, the lengthening of the conjugated chain between the two nitrogen atoms, which is known to shift the bands of extra sensitisation of a cyanine dye towards the red (Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1928, 68, 24) also does not seem to hold out great hopes, in view of the work of Bloch and Hamer (*Phot. J.*, 1930, 70, 374), who have prepared *p*-dimethylaminocinnamylidene- α -picoline-ethiodide (Q)

and found it to possess little photographic activity. Under the circumstances, it seems reasonable to suppose, that the only hopeful method of synthesising the desired sensitiser is to increase the size of the radicles attached to either or both of the two nitrogen atoms. Further work in this direction is in progress.

The preparations of quinaldine propyl iodide and quinaldine butyl iodide have been described for the first time. The crystals of these compounds are neither pleochroic nor show any reflex. The propyl iodide was prepared by heating the constituents either in a sealed tube or in an open vessel. The latter method gives a better yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-p-Diethylaminostyrylquinoline methyl iodide.—*p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.26 g.), quinaldine methiodide (2.03 g.), piperidine (0.5 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) were heated together in a flask under reflux for 5 hours. Within a quarter of an hour beautiful violet crystals appeared. After the solution had cooled, it was slowly concentrated in a vacuum desiccator. The separated crystals were recrystallised from ethyl alcohol, yield 1.26 g. (39.7%). (Found: N, 6.78; I, 28.96. $C_{22}H_{22}N_2I$ requires N, 6.31; I, 28.60 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyrylquinoline-ethyl iodide.—*p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde (2.14 g.), quinaldine ethiodide (3.61 g.) and piperidine (0.5 c.c.) were dissolved in 75 c.c. of absolute alcohol and the solution heated to brisk boiling for 3 hours. On cooling, chocolate coloured crystals were deposited, which were recrystallised from butyl alcohol, yield 4.22 g. (76.3%). (Found: N, 6.34; I, 27.95. $C_{22}H_{22}N_2I$ requires N, 6.11; I, 27.73 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyrylquinoline-n-propyl iodide.—*p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde (2.4 g.), quinaldine-*n*-propyl iodide (4.2 g.), piperidine (0.5 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) were refluxed together for 7 hours. The mixture was left in a frigidaire overnight and the separated crystals recrystallised from butyl alcohol. A second crop was obtained by concentrating the mother-liquor and recooling it in the frigidaire, total yield 4.0 g. (67%). (Found: N, 6.11; I, 27.08. $C_{24}H_{24}N_2I$ requires N, 5.93; I, 26.91 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyrylquinoline-n-butyl iodide.—A solution of quinaldine-*n*-butyl iodide (1.1 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.6 g.) and piperidine (0.75 c.c.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 9 hours. Within half an hour the solution turned scarlet and the colour deepened with the progress of heating. No crystals, however, appeared. The cold solution was slowly evaporated to about half its original volume in a vacuum desiccator and then placed in a frigidaire for 24 hours. The crystals that separated out were recrystallised from butyl alcohol, yield 0.5 g. (31.2%). (Found: N, 5.86; I, 26.25. $C_{26}H_{26}N_2I$ requires N, 5.72; I, 26.13 per cent).

Quinaldine n-propyl iodide—(Method I).—Quinaldine (8.65 g.; 1 mol.) and *n*-propyl iodide (10.63 g.; 1 mol.) were heated together on a water-bath for 30 hours. The mixture was kept in a vacuum desiccator for 48 hours and then cooled in a frigidaire. The brick-red mass, thus produced, was recrystallised from rectified spirit. A second crop of crystals was obtained by the concentration of the mother-liquor, m.p. 145°-46°, total yield 9.73 g. (49.6%). The crystals form rectangular plates, are turmeric in colour and transmit orange-yellow light only. (Found: N, 4.73; I, 41.34. $C_{18}H_{18}NI$ requires N, 4.47; I, 40.58 per cent).

(Method II).—Quinaldine (6.28 g.) and π -propyl-iodide (6.76 g.) were heated together in a sealed tube for 6 hours at 100°. The red solid after recrystallisation was found to be identical with the product obtained by the first method, yield 4.3 g. (32.9%).

Quinaldine-n-butyl iodide.—Quinaldine (8.0 g.) and *n*-butyl iodide (10.3 g.) were refluxed together on a steam-bath for 34 hours. The solution was left in a vacuum desiccator for 3 days and then in a frigidaire for 24 hours. The separated solid was filtered off, placed on a porous plate and then recrystallised from 90% alcohol, m.p. 193°, yield 3.5 g. (19.1%). The crystals are originally pink in colour but after a few days gradually turn straw. They crystallise in elongated rhombs, and transmit light of a deep orange colour. (Found: N, 4.46; I, 38.96. $C_{11}H_{13}NI$ requires N, 4.28; I, 38.84 per cent).

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